

Supplemental material

Self-inducible modulations of resting theta band activity and its relevance for behavioral adaptation

Moritz Mückschel, Annet Bluschke, Charlotte Pscherer, Sven Hoffmann, Christian Beste

Theta change and theta ratio distribution

Supplemental Figure S1: Combined scatterplot and boxplot of the average increase of theta band activity (left) and the ratio of the average increase of theta band activity and baseline theta band power (right).

Descriptive data and correlation

Supplemental Table S1: Descriptive data and Pearson correlation. Mean and standard error (SE) are given. Pearson correlations were computed with theta ratio. Correlation coefficient r and p -value are given.

mean (\pm SE)	theta ratio	PES (ms)	Accuracy	RT (ms)
LTM	$-.05 \pm .01$	24.8 ± 5.3	$.8 \pm .04$	454.6 ± 12.6
HTM	$.09 \pm .01$	44.1 ± 4.6	$.8 \pm .02$	477.3 ± 15.0
Whole sample	$.02 \pm .01$	34.5 ± 3.7	$.8 \pm .02$	465.9 ± 9.8
Pearsons correlation with theta ratio				
r		.38	-.08	-.009
p		.007	.58	.95

mean (\pm SE)	CRN Amplitude ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}^2$)	ERN Amplitude ($\mu\text{V}/\text{m}^2$)	CRN total power theta	ERN total power theta	CRN evoked power theta	ERN evoked power theta
LTM	-2.3 ± 1.7	-1.9 ± 1.7	9.9 ± 2.5	10.5 ± 1.7	7.2 ± 1.5	6.9 ± 1.5
HTM	-6.2 ± 1.7	-8.4 ± 1.7	10.7 ± 1.7	11.8 ± 1.5	10.0 ± 2.0	9.3 ± 1.5
Whole sample	-4.2 ± 1.2	-5.1 ± 1.3	10.3 ± 1.5	11.2 ± 1.1	8.6 ± 1.2	8.1 ± 1.1
Pearsons correlation with theta ratio						
r	-.22	-.33	-.01	.03	.09	.08
p	.12	.02	.95	.85	.50	.58

Scatterplot theta ratio

Supplemental Figure S2: Scatterplot of (A) theta ratio and PES and (B) theta ratio and ERN

Cluster based permutation theta activity against baseline

To test for theta band activity increase of total and evoked power in CRN and ERN trials, cluster based permutation tests were computed separately for LTM and HTM. Theta band activity (4-7 Hz) for the time window of interest from 0 to 100 ms post-response was compared against a baseline interval (-500 ms to -400 ms pre-response). Please note that baseline normalization was not applied to time frequency data for this analysis. For all conditions, the cluster-based permutation test revealed significant theta activity differences ($p < .001$) between the time window of interest and baseline. This difference was most pronounced over fronto-central electrodes. For details, please refer to supplemental Figure S2.

Supplemental Figure S3: Results of the cluster based permutations comparing mean theta band activity (4-7 Hz) in the time window of interest (0 to 100 ms) against baseline (-500 to 400 ms). Colors denote power differences, asterisk denote significant positive clusters ($p < .001$).